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The Success Phenomenon in Socio-Cultural Management

Abstract: *Introduction.* Significant for modern realities is the strengthening of people's desire for success, especially in management. However, despite desperate efforts, the vast majority of people do not succeed. This is because people do not understand what success is, its essential basis, and ways to achieve it. At the same time, the cardinal changes that are taking place today under the globalization influence necessitate a new understanding of this phenomenon's nature. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is a theoretical and philosophical analysis of the success phenomenon and identification of causal patterns of its achievement in the socio-cultural management of post-industrial society. The methodological basis of the study is the dialectical principle of cognition, systemic, metaphysical, culturological, psychological, organizational approaches to the study of behavioral processes in management. *Results.* The existing methodological approaches to the study of the phenomenon of success in the life of an individual and society as a whole are considered. The essence of success as a socio-cultural motivator of human activity and the driving force of management is revealed. Existential types of success and mechanisms of its achievement are defined. The most important personal qualities of the individual are revealed, which guarantee success in the role of a manager. The modern paradigm of management pedagogy is substantiated, with orientation on successful managers' preparation. *Conclusions.* The scientific novelty of the research results is to deepen the understanding of the nature of the success phenomenon and the peculiarities of its achievement in the conditions of complicated social relations, uncertainty, and turbulence. The significance of the study is manifested in the addition of management science to new ideas about success as a driving force in management, as well as in the possibility of using these ideas in the process of training business organizations managers.

Keywords: success phenomenon, success-efficiency, success-luck, successful manager qualities, pedagogy of successful management.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The global socio-cultural transformation taking place in the world today is strengthening people's desire for success. Achieving any success is associated with the problem of understanding it. Success is most often understood as a person's achievement of various benefits and fame. The modern era is characterized by people's desire, primarily for material, financial, administrative, career, and comfort benefits. However, their scope in the world is limited. Therefore, the possession of these goods is a competitive struggle, which often ends in wars.

Despite desperate efforts, the vast majority of people do not succeed. And many of those who seem to have succeeded do not receive inner satisfaction. This is because people do not understand what success is, its essential basis, and ways to achieve it. It is also explained by a lack of understanding of the nature of various types of human activity and the specifics of different meanings that can be embedded in the human consciousness.

Awareness of the success problem today is becoming increasingly relevant for managers – people who perform administrative functions in society and are endowed with the power, authority, and the right to manage resources. Being at the hierarchy levels, organization managers are constantly in a state of competition for the maintenance of their positions and career advancement, which ensures the growth of their personal well-being and organization success. Different historical epochs dictate different understandings of manager success. However, the lack of study of the manager's success phenomenon, as well as the dramatic changes that have occurred in society at the beginning of the 21st century, under the influence of globalization processes, necessitate a new understanding of this phenomenon's essence.

State study of the problem. The scientific discourse of the success phenomenon should begin with a careful analysis of primary sources and generalization of theoretical positions relating to this unique socio-cultural phenomenon. If you look into the philosophical literature, you can find that it has almost no sources that directly cover the problem of success. Basically, philosophers deal with the success phenomenon indirectly, using, primarily, categories such as activity and will. And it's no coincidence. After all, success is what a person wins, what achieves, what fights for, so it is not conceivable without activity and practice. Human activity is seen as a special quality, connected with the

human way of life, its self-organization. It has always been the focus of many philosophers who have tried to explore its nature: Aristotle (4th cent. BC), Rene Descartes (1637), Gottfried Leibniz (1685), Georg Hegel (1837), Karl Marx (1867), Martin Heidegger (1956), Vladislav Lektorskii (2018) and others. However, just one activity is not enough to achieve success. We need a targeted activity, which, according to many scientists, should include such consistent components as goal – motive – method – result. Each of these components is important for success. Although from a purely external point of view, the success and progress of the individual as a whole are usually judged by the activity's final results.

Along with human activity, a conscious will is considered the main factor in successful activity, as the ability by which the human mind makes its choice of goals and directs efforts to fulfill its aspirations. The nature of the will is understood as physiological, psychological, social, or transcendent. It is the inner strength of the individual. Much is said about will as in Western philosophy (Aristotle, 4th cent. BC; Plato, 4th cent. BC; Ockham, 1347; Kant, 1788; Fichte, 1804; Hegel, 1837; Schopenhauer, 1818; Nietzsche, 1888; Peirce, 1903; James, 1911; Dewey, 1919; Scheler, 1928; Sartre, 1953) and in Eastern philosophy (Upanishads, 7-3th cent. BC), as well as in the works of Slavic philosophers (Kulish, 1879; Solovyov, 1883; Bulgakov, 1912; Vernadsky, 1926; Frank, 1930; Berdiaev, 1952; Losev, 1989), whose ideas vary between the western and eastern cultural poles.

The will that exists in the form of a “practical mind” interested the representatives of German classical philosophy: Immanuel Kant (1785) and Johann Fichte (1804). In this context, in parallel with the development of the theoretical mind, which is engaged in the extrasensory, comprehensible, and ideal, they emphasized the need to develop a practical mind, which is engaged in a sensory, objective activity, controls human will and regulates its activities.

However, most practically about the will and success spoke American philosophers, especially representatives of the pragmatism philosophy Charles Peirce (1903), William James (1911), John Dewey (1919). They laid the foundation for a purposeful study of the success phenomenon. Nevertheless, unlike the representatives of German classical philosophy, pragmatism preachers ignored the cognitive nature of the mind, seeing in it only a function that serves the practical activities of human. Having rejected the traditional concepts of the theory of cognition – “subject”, “object”, “cognitive reality”, a new concept is introduced, important from the standpoint of management, the concept of “problem situation”, which should be gradually resolved with some usefulness for a person. Thus, pragmatic philosophy connects the success of cognition and human activity with the concept of usefulness, practical benefit.

Other philosophical schools look somewhat more broadly at the concept of freedom in achieving human success. So, Georg Hegel (1837) – a German philosopher, one of the creators of German idealism philosophy, saw a “practical spirit” in the human will, which is an expression of the “Absolute Spirit”. The success of an individual for him is connected with how much this person expresses the will of the Whole: the Absolute Spirit – in an ideal manifestation; state – in its particular material manifestation.

The German irrational philosopher Arthur Schopenhauer (1818), in this regard, advanced even further, giving the “World Will” an absolute ontological status and denying the notion of success in its earthly sense. According to Schopenhauer's philosophy, human life flows between desires and pleasures. Desire, by its nature, is suffering from a lack of something, and pleasure quickly overwhelms a person, and oversaturation and boredom come to life, which leads to despair. Everyone strives for ideals but does not achieve them. What is called success (happiness) in Schopenhauer is reduced to deprivation of suffering. It is possible to achieve this either by suicide – in this case, a person acts contrary to the World Will, or by asceticism – then the desires are extinguished, and as a result, suffering disappears. However, only rare individuals can resist the World Will. According to Schopenhauer, half-measures that reduce suffering and are accessible to the public, serve the moral life and contemplation of creativity, which reflect eternal ideals. All this gives his position a pessimistic color.

Eastern culture is significantly different from Western culture, and the philosophical interpretation of human activity, will, and success here is peculiar. For example, the Upanishads (7-3th cent. BC) use the concept of “Absolute Being and Will”, which together with “Absolute Knowledge and Wisdom” and “Absolute Bliss” in Hinduism constitute the triune nature of the God-Absolute – Brahman, who is the basis of all things and phenomena. From the point of view of Indian philosophy, the human will is a reflection of the Divine Will, and the success of human endeavors depends on the extent to which the human will corresponds to the Will of the Absolute. Human activity and will, does not aim to follow Absolute Freedom, is considered at best as an illusory vanity, and at worst as a grave delusion, leading to falling away from the Whole.

In addition to philosophers of the West and the East, the themes of success were also touched upon by philosophers of the Slavic tradition: Panteleimon Kulish (1879), Vladimir Solovyov (1883), Sergei Bulgakov (1912), Vladimir Vernadsky (1926), Semen Frank (1930), Nikolai Berdiaev (1952), Aleksei Losev (1989) and others. However, they seldom preached the cult of personal success as an end in itself but always associated it with the conciliar

activities of their people and with following the supreme spiritual Will of God. Concerning management, this approach was most clearly manifested in the works of Sergei Bulgakov, especially in the work “Philosophy of Economy” (1912). According to his ideas, the success of the economic activity is ensured by the unity of matter and spirit, as a guarantor of sophistry – wisdom. A wise master adheres to this unity in his activity. Material (economic) success is always one-sided, incomplete and defective, if it is achieved by infringing on the spiritual side, the interests of others, their plunder.

Modern philosophical literature has developed a well-established idea of freedom as the primary basis, which combines cognitive and motivational aspects. Practical goal-setting, which implies conscious human activity in choosing a goal, making a willful decision, and its implementation, are the core elements of management activities that directly affect its success.

After a philosophical approach, which offers the most general and fundamental principles of understanding the success phenomenon, the cultural approach is serious in this regard. The greatest contribution to the development of this approach was made by Franz Boas (1928), Talcott Parsons (1978), Ruth Benedict (1989), Clifford Geertz (2001), Sergey Anisimov (2001), Bronislaw Malinowski (2014). These researchers analyze the cultural determination problem of success, its socio-cultural models, focus on the axiological aspects of success. The general trend inherent in this approach is that success is understood as a strategy of the individual, built according to the cultural model and the ideal of a particular type of society.

Regarding the psychological approach to the study of the success phenomenon, it can be stated that it mainly focuses on research into the psychological essence of success, the factors of its formation, the development of practical recommendations and technologies for its achievement by the individual. Scientists such as Dale Carnegie (1948), Napoleon Hill (1928, 1930, 1937, 1970), Abraham Maslow (1999), Vladimir Pankratov (2000), Olena Kostyuchenko (2018), Richard Bandler, Owen Fitzpatrick, and Glenda Bradstock (2019) made a significant contribution to the development of this approach.

The organizational aspect of success is covered in the works of such well-known foreign scientists as Ichak Adizes (2004), Dan Ariely (2008, 2010), Richard Daft (2017), Peter Drucker (2017), Howard Gardner (1986), Daniel Goleman (2005), John van Maurik (2009), Daniel Pink (2015), Manfred de Vries (2006). This problem is also indirectly addressed by Ukrainian researchers, including Yaroslav Martynyshyn, Olena Khlystun, Olena Kostyuchenko, Yelena Kovalenko (Martynyshyn et al., 2020a, 2020b; Martynyshyn & Khlystun, 2018, 2019;

Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2017, 2018a, 2018b; Martynyshyn & Kovalenko, 2017, 2018a, 2018b; Martynyshyn & Kostyuchenko, 2018; Kovalenko, 2017, 2018, 2020a, 2020b) and others.

Unresolved issues. Noting the importance of scientific research of these scientists, it should be noted that in this problem there are still many unresolved issues of a theoretical and methodological nature. In particular, there is almost no unambiguous clear interpretation of the success concept, which is often identified with luck and other related terms. The very nature of the success phenomenon, its types, formation factors and achievement mechanisms are poorly studied. It requires further investigation of the individual's personal qualities, which he needs to achieve success in performing the functions of a manager. The question of the concept of modern management education focused on the training of successful managers, also remains open. The relevance and significance of the study and the solution to these issues have determined the purpose and objectives of this study.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is a theoretical and philosophical analysis of the success phenomenon and identification of causal patterns of its achievement in the socio-cultural management of post-industrial society. This purpose involves solving the following tasks:

- to consider the existing methodological approaches, to the study of the success phenomenon in the life of an individual and society as a whole;
- to reveal the essence of success as a socio-cultural motivator of human activity and the driving force of organizations management;
- to determine the existential types of the success phenomenon and its achievement mechanisms in socio-cultural management;
- to identify the most important personal qualities of the individual, which guarantee success in the role of manager;
- to substantiate the modern paradigm of management pedagogy aimed at training successful managers.

Methodology and methods. Based on the dialectical principle of cognition, the phenomenon of success is studied concerning the organization in which the success recipient (person, group of people) works (lives) and the environment in which the organization operates. At the same time, the expected success, its potential recipient, the organization, and its environment are in a state of situational unity of their inherent opposites, competition and struggle of these opposites, which may result in harmony and success, or disharmony, in case of failure.

The successor (manager), the organization, and the environment are considered through the prism of a systems approach, according to which they are a complex stochastic dynamic system consisting of a set of interconnected and interacting elements combined to achieve a common goal – success.

A metaphysical approach that, together with cultural, psychological, and organizational approaches, allows a much deeper understanding of the multifaceted nature of the success phenomenon in socio-cultural management is necessary for understanding the latent and transcendent mechanisms for achieving manager success.

To solve specific research problems, the following methods were used: classification and critical analysis – to study scientific papers on the research problem, systematization of their results; terminological – during the explication of the concept of “success”; phenomenological – to clarify the nature of the phenomenon of success as a driving force in the management of social life; semiotic analysis – to reconstruct the meanings inherent in the motives for striving for success, and their understanding; modeling – for the search for luck and means of success; theoretical generalization – to summarize.

Information base. The information base of the study consists of scientific works of the most famous domestic and foreign thinkers (philosophers, practicing managers, economists, anthropologists, psychologists, culturologists), which directly or indirectly address the problem of human success and success, group of people, especially in the management field. As an empirical basis, the results of the author's research, obtained during the observation and synthesis of the results of the work of successful top managers of Ukraine, were used in substantiating the conceptual foundations of the success phenomenon. The chronological framework of the study covers the Modern and Present and the territorial and cultural boundaries – the western and eastern worlds.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The success essence as a socio-cultural motivator of human activity

The etymology of the term “success” still remains complex and ambiguous. The Great Explanatory Dictionary of the modern Ukrainian language interprets this word as a positive result of work, deals, etc.; significant achievements, luck, talent; public recognition, approval of something, someone's achievements (Busel, 2005, p. 1516). Similar interpretations of the term “success” are given by many other etymological dictionaries. Sergei Ozhegov's popular Dictionary of the Russian Language (1949) interprets this term as good luck in achieving

something; public recognition (p. 741). The well-known English-Russian Dictionary by Vladimir Müller (1944) gives approximately the same meaning (p. 588). However, if we open older dictionaries, such as Vladimir Dal's Explanatory Dictionary of the Living Great Russian Language (1866), we will not find the word “success” there.

So, at the end of the 19th century, “success” was not yet realized as the word of a living language, and in the middle of the twentieth century, it was already available, literally and figuratively. Although it is clear that the very phenomenon of success arose long before the emergence of terms that denote it.

The variety of interpretations of the word “success” is well shown by modern dictionaries of synonyms of Ukrainian and Russian languages (Aleksandrova, 2001; Karavanskyj, 2012; and others). Howsoever, such ambiguity of the term “success” complicates the possibility of its deep understanding. Therefore, it is advisable to distribute all the disparate meanings of this word into typical relatively homogeneous groups, which will distinguish the most significant and reasonable definition of the concept of “success” (*Table 1*).

Table 1. Grouping of disparate meanings of the word “success”

Grouping features	Groups of definitions
Achieving the goal through efficiency	Positive, desirable result of efficiency in work, business, struggle, etc.
Achieving the goal through luck	Positive, desirable result of luck, happy coincidence, luck, destiny
Recognition of achievements	Public recognition, approval, furor, laurels (valor, glory)

Source: own development

Systematic analysis of various meanings and senses of the word “success” allows to divide them into the following three typical groups of success: 1) achieving the goal through the person’s efficiency (group of people) all their strength, knowledge, abilities, efforts and energy; 2) achieving the goal through human luck, happy coincidence, luck; 3) public recognition of achievement, approval, furor, laurels.

As a result of grouping the meanings of the word “success”, we find two main semantic components in this word. The first is the set goal achievement: a positive, desired result of work, business. The second semantic component is the public recognition of what has been achieved, which again refers to human desires, to the goals to which man aspired. These two semantic components are necessary and sufficient conditions for success. That means

that success alone is not enough to achieve the desired goal. It also requires recognition of what has been achieved by society, without which it is impossible to feel complete satisfaction with what has been achieved (*Figure 1*).

Figure 1. Components of the “success” concept
Source: own development

At the same time, the achievement of the purpose can be obtained both due to the efficiency of the person or collective and due to luck, a happy combination of circumstances, luck, fate. Given this and the above arguments, we can offer the following definition of the concept under study: Success is the achievement of the desired goal of a person through his efficiency and (or) luck and public recognition of what has been achieved. It is accompanied by a sense of human need for society and receiving positive emotions, which, in turn, is the causative agent of the emergence of new strength, energy, as well as an effective motivator for its creative search and ups.

3.2. Existential types of success and mechanisms for achieving it in management

The desire to succeed today is typical to almost everyone. That is especially evident in the category of people who perform managerial functions in society and are managers of organizations or seek to become managers or expand their career path. Any public organization and its management are considered to have succeeded if they have achieved the goal and received recognition of their achievements both directly in the business environment and society as a whole. As mentioned above, the achievement of the purpose can be achieved through the efficiency and (or) luck of the individual or collective. Therefore, it is fully reasonable to distinguish two existentially different types of success – success-efficiency and success-luck.

Success-efficiency is a success that is persistently achieved, people fight for it, overcoming various obstacles, wasting physical, mental, and spiritual strength and energy. The path to it is usually long and difficult. It requires from the manager the appropriate knowledge, skills, abilities, rationally calculated, systematic, strong-willed efforts.

Success-luck may not require efficiency and effort. People may not seek it, not fight for it, but merely wait, hoping that it will come. Here, personal qualities, the will of the manager may not be needed, and if they are needed, then completely different than in the previous case. Rational calculation, systematics, and methodology are also not required. The point here is quite different – in luck, destiny, happy choice. And in this case, it is hard to determine the factor that led to success.

These two types of success have a fundamentally different content, indicate completely different life values and goals, and, accordingly, different ways of organizational behavior of the manager (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2. Types of success in management

Source: own development

Analyzing the history of social development, it is not difficult to notice that at the earliest stage of its formation, in the conditions of appropriating economy, when a man consumed only ready-made products of nature (hunted wild animals, collected edible fruits, fished), success-luck was the predominant type of success. So, a hunter or fisherman hoped, first of all, for luck, it was vital to him: he was looking for it and waiting for it. Later, in the process of further development of society and the emergence of a new form of management, based on production (agriculture, livestock, handicrafts) and consumption of man-made products, success-efficiency becomes the predominant type of success. And here, unlike the hunter and the fisherman, the farmer, the herdsman, and the craftsman have to develop success incessantly and methodically every day. The hope for luck is replaced by the calculation of efficiency as a result of hard work.

The Renaissance and the Enlightenment played an important role in establishing the orientation of man to success-efficiency in Western culture. However, this orientation reached its apogee in the next historical period – in the era of Industrialism. The main determinants that contributed to this were:

1) humanism – a system of ideas and views on man as the highest value, belief in the power of knowledge and the infinite possibilities of man, his will and mind, the meaning of being, purpose and value of human life on the wrong side, not somewhere else, but this real, sensual, objective world, here and now man can and must seek and find the true meaning of his happiness; human's interest is directed to himself, activity – to the surrounding reality, to its transformation, subordination, and work on itself becomes more and more meaningful when it gives concrete tangible results in this real world;

2) modern European science, which leads to the world desecration;

3) rationalism, which emphasizes the superiority of mind (logical thinking) in human cognition and actions;

4) a new picture of the world, in which something like the ontological landing of a person was realized, which was necessary for the constitution of success-efficiency as the meaning and purpose of life;

5) great scientific and technical discoveries;

6) transition to factory production and the emergence of industry;

7) social Darwinism as a natural law of interspecies struggle and competition;

8) capitalist mode of production, political economy, and market model of management;

9) Protestant ethics, as a compromise between religion, science, and the capitalist mode of production;

10) secular type of state.

Success-efficiency is a category mainly of the Western world. It is inherently directly related to the vocation and is its practical implementation, so this type of success requires effort, cannot be random, and comes naturally, according to the abilities and hard work of a person.

A vocation is what makes a person an individual, a favorite, and socially valuable business in which a person is a professional. It is a tendency and an inner attraction to any business, profession, which are justified by the presence of the necessary abilities. The vocation is also what they serve. It imposes responsibility; it is necessary to be at the height of the situation; it must be answered. Such efforts and aspirations contribute to the formation of the manager's personal qualities, make him successful.

However, the true vocation of a manager must be found and earned. It is not for everyone. To do this, you need, first of all, to have:

– rich desires, will (a vigorous human, as a rule, has energetic, developed desires; this person wants a lot, has something to wake up every day and does not just work out, what others expect from him, that person does what he wants);

– cheerful, lively, and assembled body (if a person is sluggish, eyes are sleepy, gestures are relaxed, then any vocation is closed to him; such a body blocks any vocation; vocation is a soul, but if a person has a disorganized body for management, then this soul will be blocked by the body);

– well-developed universal abilities (goal-setting, planning, support for cheer and high energy, positive worldview, easy ability to learn);

– ability and habit to always bring the creative skill to the highest level, to the level of “excellent”, to the level of skill;

– caring for people (vocation should be aimed not only at meeting their own needs but also at what people need).

Success-luck is an existential value of a completely different world. A world that is experienced as irrational and full of uncertainty, in which everything, including human life, is the result of a game of incomprehensible (in terms of rational, logical thinking) transcendent, magical forces (Order and Chaos, Good and Evil, Yin and Yang, etc.). The value of this type of success was initially unique to Eastern culture. Today, in the context of society's transition to post-industrialism, the growing interdependence of cultures, and the crisis of the Enlightenment, success-luck is becoming a significant type of success in the West. The main determinants that contribute to this are:

1) post-classical philosophy, which, in contrast to the classics that put mind and rationality first and set as the main goal of identifying the internal logic of processes, marks the rejection of the recognition of reasonable grounds for reality and brings to the fore an irrational moment; the mind, in many areas of reality cognition, begins to be assigned a utilitarian place, and intuitive or non-theoretical knowledge – the main one;

2) irrationalism, which proclaims the supremacy of sensual (intuitive thinking) in human cognition and actions; emphasizes the existence of worldview areas inaccessible to the mind, and achievable only through such means as intuition, feelings, faith, instinct, revelation, etc.;

3) the picture of the world, which eliminates the problem of meaning, insists on the absurdity, arbitrariness of being and constructs a new ontology in which the sign replaces, makes superfluous the indicated; in this ontological failure, which is the essence of the post-industrial era, there is no room for a realistic, rational-active spirit of the Renaissance; here a new sense of life is inevitable, and hence a change of values; here they no longer strive for

those efforts and returns which are characteristic of Industrialism but crave good luck (actively or passively);

4) scientific and information revolution and globalization, which cause a significant complication of social relations, the society transition to a new, largely incomprehensible, social order and way of life.

Success-luck is, to some extent, the antithesis of success based on efficiency. It is a matter of Fate and Will (man, organization, country, society, world) – in terms of irrational methodological approach, and a matter of chance, its game – from the standpoint of a rational approach. Therefore, under the first approach, success-luck should be considered as ontologically logical. Moreover, this pattern is hidden. It cannot be comprehended by scientific methods and abstract-logical thinking. It can be felt only emotionally, intuitively, but not everyone can do it. With the second approach, success-luck seems ontologically random, so any actions and personal qualities of the manager aimed at overcoming this accident and obtaining success-luck are rendered untenable and inappropriate. Here the only thing is to wait, hoping that luck itself will come. But with the first approach, individual personal qualities are needed. However, they are completely different from those needed for success-efficiency. Given this, two types of success-luck can be distinguished: passive and active.

Passive success-luck does not require any individual personal qualities of the success recipient. To expect good luck, you do not need to be someone, just be. Inherently, luck, in this case, is what comes in the game, and not in sports, where skill is required, but in card games, roulette, lotteries. A happy occasion is the life goal, the dreams limit, and the whole strategy of activity. Do not work on yourself, systematically going to success, but look for opportunities. Hence, in many ways, the increased social mobility of modern society, the constant change of occupation, place of residence, even marriage partners. In the same way, to a large extent, it is the spiritual reason for the public consciousness criminalization. Such a worldview, based on “fart” and is specific to the criminal world, determines its way of lifestyle and represents a key difference between the psychology of the criminal, “gentleman of fortune”, from the psychology of the employee. Such orientation eliminates the personality, leads to its degradation, and, of course, cannot be the basis of the manager's behavior model.

Active success-luck, on the contrary, requires special individual personal qualities of the successor, but not such as for success-efficiency – associated with rational-logical intelligence, but related to professional feeling and intuition, that is, such human abilities that allow knowing the irrational, first of all, Fate (predetermined course of events in the human life, organization, country,

etc.) and Will (which underlies all the opposing forces of the world), and to feel and “catch” luck. These unique abilities are determined by the level of development of human emotional intelligence and are very important for the success of a modern manager.

So, in the context of socio-cultural management, the most relevant are the active types of success obtained due to the efficiency and luck of managers, their knowledge of existential truth, and the identification of the development laws of managed objects and the environment: 1) visible laws – using scientific methods and abstract logical intelligence; 2) invisible patterns – using intuition and emotional intelligence.

Nevertheless, no less significant, but the most difficult from the point of view of consciousness, is the passive type of success obtained by managers due to wholly unexpected, unpredictable, intellectually meaningless luck as a result of ordinary inaction and playing a happy case. In this regard, it is worth noting that today, when not only the moral but also the ontological line between conditional and unconditional is blurred, when the purpose of life becomes rest – even “leisure civilization” – the game turns from means to goal, and for many life becomes a game. Accordingly, the status of professional players – artists, athletes, showmen, businessmen, politicians, who are becoming a prominent part of the modern elite, rises. They are fashion legislators, samples of life standards, behavioral stereotypes. Among them, young people are looking for idols. And if before it was considered necessary to constantly remind that life is not a game and nothing is given without work, today, in the era of existential onset of “society of luck”, another pedagogy begins to dominate, namely gaming, which, along with positive moments, inevitably leads to the infantilization of consciousness, which is unacceptable in the case of the manager training and the development of his core abilities.

3.3. The most important personal qualities of a successful manager

The problem of the qualities that a person needs to achieve success has long been studied in management. And even though sciences such as work psychology, organizational psychology, psychotechnics, psychometrics have made a significant contribution to the development of methods for assessing personal qualities, there are still no clearly defined unified criteria for personal qualities that allow succeeding in management.

What qualities should a successful manager have?

The great thinker and artist, one of the few outstanding geniuses of mankind *Leonardo da Vinci* (1503, p. 42) distinguished seven qualities that are necessary for self-expression and self-development: curiosity; verifying yourself with real experience; sensitivity; acceptance of uncertainty; harmonious thinking; the feeling of your body, the perception of reality in the relationship.

As we see, here we are talking not about any qualifications or competencies, but about such qualities as the ability to penetrate the essence of phenomena, processes, people, achieve harmony within oneself and with the outside world, to be creative and original. It is obvious that not everyone has such qualities. Of course, they are universal and do not belong to any particular type of activity. Perhaps in other areas, their role may not be so significant, but in management, it is difficult to overestimate it.

The great L. da Vinci created in the middle of the last millennium. The creative fruits of genius are not influenced by time. But it is crucial to bear in mind that the world is constantly changing. A couple of centuries after the era of da Vinci, Europe entered the industrial epoch. It took the past time of the masters. Specialized qualified personnel replaced masters. Differently, people began to look at what is necessary for professional success. This led to significant transformations. The masters were changed by specialists, and, it seemed, the ideas of L. da Vinci remained in the past. However, the world continued to change, relations between people began to be filled with new content, business in terms of its tasks became increasingly sophisticated and graceful from the point of view of its methods, as well as the tasks it solved. At the turn of the 21st century, with great speed over the decades (and not hundreds, much fewer thousands of years, as it was before), not just significant or even dramatic changes began to occur – global transformations have taken place. Naturally, it has undergone adjustments and a set of key qualities that form the individual potential, based on which he can achieve the desired result.

The author of best-sellers on business world issues, *Daniel Pink* (2015, p. 108) formulated six personal qualities of a manager for success in the 21st century. The most important among them are the ability to see meaning, to understand what the activity is for, to understand purpose as development; ability to design on the basis of feelings; ability to go beyond logic, use emotions and intuition; the ability to capture and convince the story; ability to show humor, to contribute game moments to the business; the ability to think broadly and creatively, not to dwell on details.

Obviously, in the 21st century, six personal qualities correlate with those distinguished by L. da Vinci. Now, we see that the industrial era is a thing of the

past, and the era of masters is returning with a strong emphasis on creativity, individualization and reliance on the hidden abilities and qualities of the soul. Speaking about the manager's personal qualities, according to D. Pink, it should be noted that there is a noticeable emphasis on quality, characterizing precisely the emotional, artistic side of the individual behavior. The rational basis of behavior undeniably fades into the background, success basis is emotional intelligence. This leads to the conclusion that in today's environment and current conditions to succeed, the manager needs to develop his emotional intelligence to more fully involve him in practical activities.

In the last decade, one of the most popular concepts for the managers' key qualities development is the WIST concept, put forward by *John van Maurik* (2009). According to this concept, a successful manager has such qualities as wisdom, integrity, sensitivity, tenacity (p. 68).

This concept, as we see, does not affect either the branch of the manager's knowledge or the field of his professional qualifications. The manager's success is based on individual qualities that characterize his ability to build a positive relationship with people, relying mainly on the emotional and sensory aspects of his behavior. This concept strengthened manager orientation towards the development of their interpersonal intelligence and ethical behavior in management.

The study and synthesis of the best practices of the top managers of successful companies in Ukraine (194 respondents were interviewed) made it possible to formulate their own concept on personal qualities, which allow individuals to be successful in the role of a manager (*Table 2*).

The most important of these is the alternative vision. And if a modern manager has this ability, then he should be called not just a manager but a visionary. Analyzing the history of various companies' failures, we can find that the reasons for their failure were not bad strategies or insufficient upgrades. The companies' failure was the result of the leaders' actions, largely due to their vision. And to be more precise, the absence of one.

Arthur Schopenhauer (1851) has a rather figurative statement: "Talent hits a target no one else can hit; Genius hits a target no one else can see" (p. 406). Managing a business organization, especially in modern conditions, is an extremely complex process, and it is constantly becoming more and more complex, more and more sophisticated, like something like "go there – I don't know where, and bring it – I don't know what", but definitely necessary for success. The logic is not applicable here. This requires a completely different vision, a non-standard approach, talent. Therefore, the alternative vision as the ability

to look into the very essence of the relationship, as the ability to look at tomorrow from the day after tomorrow, see and understand the invisible is the main personal quality based on which managers can succeed in business.

Table 2. Personal qualities of a successful manager

Types of qualities	Characteristic
Alternative vision	The ability to penetrate deeply into the essence of various situations, processes, phenomena, to be able to notice and understand the invisible in them (new opportunities, threats, trends) and intuitively predict their development
Non-standard thinking	Ability to deviate from traditional schemes of thinking, go beyond logic, beyond the visible and be able to think divergently, irrationally, illogically, nonlinearly, critically, emotionally, intuitively
Creativity	Ability to constantly change, differentiate and produce fundamentally new, unusual ideas and bring them to a concrete practical result in the form of various attractive things
Communication	Artistry, emotionality, sensitivity, the ability to build and develop relationships, persuade, evoke empathy, influence the will, consciousness and feelings
Orientation in chaos	Ability to navigate and quickly solve complex problem situations in conditions of chaos (inconsistency, disorder, disorganization, instability, variability, uncertainty, turbulence, etc.)
Obsession	Emotional and volitional state, which is manifested in complete self-forgetful devotion to the cause and persistent in self-sacrifice intention to achieve the goal, overcoming any obstacles and difficulties
Confidence	A property whose core is a positive assessment of one's own skills, abilities as sufficient to achieve significant ("impossible") goals and success

Source: own development

An alternative vision of a manager is a very subtle matter that has no explicit and unambiguous attributes. The basis of alternative vision is a developed emotional intelligence, the ability to feel fate and will, the ability to comprehend the situation, see the hidden driving forces, trends, and patterns, understand people, feel the springs that determine the strength and direction of the situation, "catch" luck and achieve success. In this regard, it is impossible to give universal measures through which it is possible to unambiguously identify such a vision, the degree of its manifestation. However, the presence

of a vision can be said when someone manages to achieve results that are considered impossible to achieve. At the same time, looking from the side, it is difficult to explain how he manages to achieve such results.

You can specify what is typical of managers who have an alternative vision. First, they pursue “impossible” goals. Second, they are obsessed with devotion. It is a deep devotion to people, company, the chosen cause. Third, they are given obsessions. In critical conditions, they become even more obsessed, even more, mobilized to solve problems. Fourth, they are characterized by deep insight into the perception and evaluation of people. Management is people, people, and only people. In people, there are opportunities, and in people, there are threats. People are a source of strength, and people are a source of weakness. Therefore, a deep understanding of people, the ability to feel a person is the most considerable quality of a visionary. Fifth, alternative vision is not without the ability to deviate from traditional thinking schemes, go beyond logic, beyond the visible, and the ability to think divergently, irrationally, logically, nonlinearly, critically, emotionally, intuitively, since all these are the principal tools of vision. Therefore, non-standard thinking is a characteristic feature of managers who have a vision.

Of course, the vision itself does not produce results. We need existent actions. But, thanks to the vision, the manager can build his actions in such a way that they will lead to the desired result. And here, a crucial quality of the manager is his ability to navigate and to quickly solve difficult problem situations in the conditions of chaos: inconsistency, disorder, disorganization, instability, uncertainty, variability, turbulence, and more. The manager should consider such situations not just as a mess in which it is impossible to carry out activities, but on the contrary as a more complex and less accessible order, and being confident and able not to be lost in such situations, be able to see new opportunities in them and quickly apply adequate actions to realize the identified opportunities in favor of his business.

Momentous features are also the creativity and communication of the manager, as his ability to constantly develop new ideas and the ability to build and develop relationships that, in harmonious combination with previous qualities, make it possible to achieve great success in business and the career of a manager of a business organization.

Here it is appropriate to note that in light of the above, managers are not all those who are engaged in management activities or are business owners. The majority of managers are administrators, and most business owners are just owners, not even investors and not entrepreneurs at all. Therefore, we need

a suitable system of management training aimed at the formation and development of personal qualities that can ensure its success as a manager.

3.4. Pedagogy of successful management

The meaning of training a successful manager can be defined as the pedagogical activities implementation to increase the competitiveness of the learner. We may be denied that any educational process is aimed at this to some extent. In fact, not everyone. In the vast majority of cases, even when there are tasks to increase the competitiveness of the future specialist, it is not primary. When it comes to training managers, competitiveness is the basis of the foundations, which determines the degree of their adaptability to the complex competitive conditions of the business environment and hence the ability to survive.

Business and competition are actually synonymous. The manager is constantly faced with competition in the external environment, and how he manages to cope with it, depends on his success or, conversely, failure. The manager is also always in contact with internal competition in the company, since he, by the nature of his activity, is on the career ladder, the promotion of which requires him to be not just a high-class specialist, but an employee who can be the best in a competition collision. Competition, entrepreneurial energy, and creative work are the three pillars on which progress is made.

In the case of a manager, to be successful means to act in such a way that the competitive situations in which he is constantly developing in his favor or develop in the desired direction for him. From this understanding, it follows that the manager's success is determined by two components: the situation and the action. The studied issue leads to an important conclusion. Without a deep understanding of the situation and adequate actions, there can be no manager's success.

Thus, the pedagogy of successful management should help the future manager develop personal qualities that make it possible to understand the situations in which the manager finds himself, determine and carry out actions that allow him to occupy winning positions in a competitive environment. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that the management of a business organization does not deal with logic but with the people's interests. This is an extremely considerable position to follow to be a successful manager.

Traditionally, our education is focused on the formation of specialists, that is, preparing them for definite actions, in a certain field of activity. More precisely, to train specialists for specific work within a particular profession and specialty. To do this, the learner must be given an idea (abstract and con-

crete, with a set of formal definitions) about the subject of further activities and taught adequate tools used in this subject area. In other words, to provide him with complete information about the subject (traditionally called knowledge) and help him acquire the appropriate skills and abilities, which are, relatively, the specialty attributes.

The formation of a specialist of a particular qualification, in this case, is the main task of the pedagogical process. By the way, this approach to understanding the pedagogy of management dominates today in our education. Although, it should be noted that recently, due to the transformation in the education system, there has been a transition to the so-called competence approach. The statement indicates that the reforms aimed at modernizing education, bringing it closer to a state that meets the requirements of post-industrial society.

However, it should be emphasized that neither competency nor qualification approaches fully meet the educational training needs of a successful manager. Such a situation is unacceptable since it leads to an increase in the number of inefficient managers who do not meet the challenges of today, cannot identify problems and solve them effectively, are confused in different ways of why, what, and how they should do. As a result, there is an increasing number of inefficient organizations that are unable to achieve self-development in the context of globalization changes.

Management is by no means a specialty, nor even a profession in the classical understanding of these terms. This is a specific area of activity, which has a predominantly situational nature. To achieve success in this field, the actions of the individual must be, more, art, distinguished by originality and even uniqueness, that is, often carried out differently. Since the subject matter is characterized by great diversity, it cannot be described not only thoroughly but at least approximately. It is more or less clear what minimum set of knowledge should be mastered and what skills should be acquired. But all this is only a certain qualification minimum, which does not give grounds for achieving the desired results of practical activity in the manager status.

In our understanding, management pedagogy should not only contribute to the development of all these abilities, but above all, be aimed at their development. At the same time, it is crucial that now the world education system has some necessary set of methodological techniques and tools that make it possible to provide students with efficient assistance in these qualities development. Most of these methodological techniques and learning technologies are unique. They are not only far different from the methods of traditional education but often opposite to them.

However, quite often, you have to hear from many business leaders, the main drawback of graduates who have completed management education is their complete lack of ability to disclose and identify problems. And this is the most important task of the manager because the problems themselves hide various business opportunities. According to company executives, even if universities train literate young people who know a lot, they do not give them important things: understanding the processes taking place in business, especially the ability to see problems, dig up to their reasons, and only then offer possible solutions.

Instead, university graduates (unfortunately, this primarily applies to those who have studied well) come with ready answers. With the correct answers, that they were taught and for memorizing which they received positive marks. Businessmen are well aware that catastrophic mistakes are made when there is a ready answer, and at the same time, the problem is not worked out in-depth.

The question arises: why do universities not develop students' ability to solve and identify problems? The answer is in the runoff. In most academic management disciplines, problems are identified, formulated, and described. Consequently, the student's focal attention is aimed at studying the methods of solving already formulated problems. Herewith, very little and even no attention is paid to considering the issue of limiting the possibility of using the proposed methods outside the audience a priori of definite tasks and problems.

As a result of such studying, students firmly believe in the universality of the methods application they have studied, and believe that they have acquired the ability to solve, if not all, then the vast majority of the real problems. This is just one of the most significant shortcomings of management pedagogy in Ukraine.

A significant feature of the academic sphere of society is its duality. On the one hand, it is the most important source of change, renewal, development, and progress for humankind. On the other hand, this sphere is very conservative, hard to change. Therefore, there is a paradox: education and science as social institutions are pushing society forward, and they are slightly keeping pace with those changes in public life.

Business is one of the most dynamically developing spheres of society. It is in business that breakthroughs are carried out, relying precisely on the achievement of scientific thought. Business transposes society, transferring it from one stage to another. Therefore, management pedagogy is most in need of updating, bringing its methodology and technology to the needs of a business

that are constantly changing. And this allows us to argue that management pedagogy is, in many ways, a source of development in the field of education as a whole.

Now there is a paradigm shift in management pedagogy. The educational process of industrial society is focused on the questions: “what?” and “how?”. Therefore, the education system's task, adequate to the needs of this type of society, is to train workers of a specific specialty and qualification.

The process of educational training of a post-industrial society manager does not deny the preliminary paradigm, but the priority is to focus on the questions: “why?” and “what for?”. And this brings to the forefront the main task of the educational process – to increase the general level of the future manager development and form a specific type of behavior.

The paradigms' comparison of the management pedagogy of industrial and post-industrial society allows us to see their striking difference (*Table 3*).

The first is focused on the transfer of subject knowledge (in fact, it is the transfer of systematized information in individual educational disciplines) and the development of particular skills corresponding to a given qualification model, that is, the one who learns should know and be able (often supplemented by the formula “be able to apply in practice”).

The second paradigm of management pedagogy is aimed, relatively speaking, at educating the future manager, forming a certain model of his behavior. This type of paradigm is characterized by the student's specific personal qualities development, instilling in him suitable values, appropriate behavior standards, the need for creative activity, a steady understanding that the basis of everything is the activity. And this cannot be achieved through the simple transfer of systematic information and the acquisition of some set of skills (through traditional lectures, practical classes, and seminars). This requires group work on projects, immersion in real practical activity, attending master classes of authoritative people, that is, filling the learning process with a creative and emotional context.

Does this mean that the self-development of an individual in the educational process of managers does not imply their assimilation of certain systematized information, usually called knowledge, or the development of professional skills and abilities? The answer is obvious – of course not. Education cannot go without expanding the student's awareness, without obtaining ideas, definitions, concepts, etc. It will also be defective without mastering several operations and a definite set of actions. Undoubtedly, all this is necessary, but it is not the main thing.

Table 3. Priorities of management pedagogy paradigms

Existing paradigm	New paradigm
Management is a <i>science</i>	Management is an <i>art</i>
Development of <i>abstract-logical intelligence</i> of the individual	Development of the individual <i>emotional intelligence</i>
<i>The main task of the educational process:</i> transfer of subject knowledge and development of abilities and skills corresponding to the set model of the manager qualification	<i>The main task of the educational process:</i> formation of a specific behavior model and the development of alternative abilities that ensure success in the role of manager
<i>The educational process unfolded into the past</i> (outdated theories, experience) with an attempt to project this for the future	<i>The educational process unfolded into the future</i> with an attempt to design “tomorrow” with the “day after tomorrow”
<i>The main forms and sequence of the educational process:</i> first a lecture (presentation of the theory from a certain subject area), and only then – a practical lesson	<i>The main forms and sequence of the educational process:</i> first a practical lesson and only after that – a theoretical justification for its implementation (lecture)
<i>Formal learning technology</i> , with a focus on memorizing material without understanding the action, its scheme and structure; learning occurs through the repetition of the correct answers to the questions “how?”, “what?” and to a lesser extent – “why?”	<i>Informal learning technology</i> , learning by action, with a detailed explanation of its scheme and structure; learning is mainly through asking the right questions “why?”, “what for?” and only after that – finding the answer “how?”
<i>Learning microclimate:</i> mostly passive	<i>Learning microclimate:</i> creative activity, interest
<i>Learning outcomes</i> – obtaining other people's bookish knowledge (information), which mainly diverge from practice; disappointment	<i>Learning outcomes</i> – developing knowledge and personal experience that coincide with and is even ahead of practice; pleasure

Source: own development

In today's world, you can always get the information you need through data array access. In addition, information in terms of its relativity and usefulness is constantly becoming outdated. And the technologies used in the management sphere are also developing at a very high pace. Therefore, now all this should no longer be the main component of management pedagogy. At the initial stage of its formation, knowledge and skills were at the center of the educational process. Now they should be replaced by personal characteristics, emotional intelligence, real activity, and above all, its moral and ethical side.

The world-famous psychologist *Howard Gardner* (1986), the author of the monograph “Multiple Intelligence: New Horizons in Theory and Practice”, which made a truly revolutionary breakthrough in understanding intelligence, and as a result, in realizing the essence of education, concluded that in the modern world, intelligence is higher than interpersonal intelligence.

Daniel Goleman (2005), in the super bestseller “Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ”, cites the following statement by Gardner: “Many people with a mental development rate of 160 work for those whose ratio does not exceed 100, if the first has low interpersonal intelligence, then the second – high. In everyday life, there is no higher intelligence than interpersonal. That is, we merely need to teach children at school to use personal mental abilities” (p. 75).

In modern life, especially in management, the ability to use emotional intelligence, as well as the ability to understand, feel and use the emotions of others, are powerful sources of competitiveness and, consequently, the key factors for success in life. Emotional intelligence is the basis for the creation, development, destruction of relationships and interactions between people. The statement means that its development and use must be at the center of the manager's education. However, the practical pedagogical process is aimed mainly at the rational mental abilities development (it is about logic, the logic of thinking, and behavior), the improvement of emotional abilities is virtually excluded from the learning tasks. In the case of management pedagogy, such a state of affairs is unacceptable because management is not based on logic but on the people's interests. And in general, real life does not fit into logical schemes.

Professor *Dan Ariely*, who received widespread worldwide appreciation after the publication of the bestseller *Predictably Irrational* (2008), wrote in his also well-known monograph, *The Upside of Irrationality* (2010): “Of course, it would be great if we were rational and follow what should be done. Unfortunately, it is not... How else can you explain the fact that millions of sports clubs' membership cards bought to maintain health are unused. Or the risk to which many expose themselves and others by sending SMS while driving a car. You can continue indefinitely. It follows that it is wrong to assume that a human is a perfectly intelligent computer. On the contrary, by observing how people behave, very often our observations lead us to the conclusion that people are irrational” (p. 7). At the end of the monograph, he concludes that there are many manifestations of our irrational behavior: “We have many persistent, irrational manifestations; we often do not know how these irrationalities affect us and therefore do not fully realize what determines our behavior” (p. 289). This means that you need to learn (for managers, this is especially important)

to succeed in irrationality conditions, that is, to develop in yourself those qualities that rely on emotional intelligence.

We noted that management pedagogy and traditional pedagogy are very different in the vector of their main efforts. Managers in their work are focused on creating, creating the future. They must have an alternative vision, be emotionally minded, in direct communication, reveal problems, and look for opportunities. And they must constantly take into account people's interests and assess the degree of emotions influence on their behavior. And traditional pedagogy, deployed in the past (proven theorems, formulated propositions, written theories, etc.), manipulates abstract symbols, proceeds from the prism of absolute impartiality, aims at analysis, neutrality in communications, often written.

When moving from traditional to modern management pedagogy, the teacher-student relationship is replaced by the boss-specialist relationship. The central element of learning is the ability development to solve the problem and formulate tasks, which solution should lead to the problem elimination. Communication – through setting the “right” questions and not by repeating the “right” answers. Studying – based on an experiment mainly in the form of group work on projects.

Of course, traditional teaching methods such as group discussion, analysis of specific situations, tests, and homework in essay writing cannot be excluded. But all this, together with creative, experimental activity, must necessarily end with a reflection, the student's answer to the question: “What has changed in me?”, “What have I seen differently?”, “What have I not achieved yet?”. It is the reflection that serves as an indicator of how the learning has taken place.

It is important to understand that learning through the acquisition of knowledge in the form of systematic information, and even more, in the form of fragmentary information, is very often not only useless but also dangerous. Since it creates the illusion of development. Of course, in this case, we are not talking about useless, harmful, or inaccurate information. We are talking about the correct and, as many believe, necessary information for obtaining an education.

For several reasons, knowledge should not be considered the sole basis of a manager's educational process. After all, knowledge has a dual character. You can understand life, mainly looking back. But at the same time, life is only moving forward. It follows that knowledge both helps and inhibits adequate inclusion in the life process. There is a metaphor, relying on knowledge, we seem to move forward in the car, looking in the rearview mirror. If the road is relatively flat, then it is possible. But on a winding road, what modern life is, it will constantly lead to failures or even disasters.

Another point is connected with the fact that management is creativity, art. And, as you know, real creativity and art go beyond the “right – wrong” plane. Finally, it is important to understand that the more we know, the more the space of our ignorance becomes. We find ourselves trapped in limited knowledge. The solution: you need to move in the space of wisdom, and the knowledge itself does not give such an opportunity and does not allow you to achieve management success.

4. Conclusions

The article provides a theoretical and philosophical analysis of the success phenomenon as a driving force in the socio-cultural management of the modern world. The study results make it possible to draw the following conclusions:

1. Success occupies an important place both in the individual life and in the life of the whole society. In this sense, human history is a history of successes and failures. Philosophical, cultural, psychological, and organizational methodological approaches can be applied to study this phenomenon.

2. The concept of “success” is filled with many meanings. In our understanding, success is the achievement of the desired goal of a person, or group of people, due to their dedication and (or) luck and public recognition of what has been achieved.

3. Success-efficiency and success-luck are the existential value of different worlds, organizational behavior, and ways of the manager thinking – ordered and chaotic, rational and irrational, logical and intuitive, applying efforts and tuning the senses.

4. The most important personal qualities of the individual, which can guarantee success in the manager role, are alternative vision, non-standard thinking, creativity, sociability, orientation in chaos, obsession, self-confidence.

5. The pedagogy of successful management, first of all, should be aimed at developing these abilities. The educational process should be oriented to the future with an attempt to project “tomorrow” with the “day after tomorrow”, to teach action, develop emotional intelligence, gain knowledge and personal experience, which will coincide with practice, and even outrun it.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of the study consists in deepening the understanding of the success phenomenon nature and the peculiarities of its achievement in socio-cultural management in conditions of complicated social relations, increasing uncertainty and turbulence.

The significance of the study. The significance of the study is manifested in the addition of management science to new theoretical provisions on success as a driving force in management, as well as the possibility of using them in the process of training managers of business organizations.

Prospects for further research. The prospect of further research in this direction may be to find out the factors for achieving success in various areas of human life.

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